

The following trend cards were developed by DLR-PT for an interactive Foresight workshop at the EU-WB Ministerial Meeting in Skopje in September 2024.

For more information on the method of Strategic Foresight and the use of these trend cards for anticipatory R&I policy-making, feel free to reach out to Dr. Julia Schmälder or Simon Winter from the POLICY ANSWERS team

(Julia.Schmaelter@dlr.de; Simon.Winter@dlr.de)

EU Accession

The path to EU accession for the Western Balkans remains uncertain, with competing priorities and enlargement fatigue among current EU members. The recent candidacies of Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia further complicate the timeline, affecting the region's regulatory environment, investment climate, and market confidence, which could stall reforms and slow economic integration with the EU.

Political Volatility

Ongoing political instability in the Western Balkans, marked by unresolved regional conflicts and governance issues, is creating an unpredictable environment. This volatility deters long-term investment, complicates business planning, and undermines economic growth, while political uncertainty delays reforms and hinders economic integration both within the region and with the EU.

Weak Culture of Compliance

Weak compliance with EU standards in the Western Balkans, particularly in areas such as anti-corruption, rule of law, and institutional integrity, continues to be a challenge. Poor law enforcement and perceived corruption undermine fair competition and discourage investment, while slow progress in judicial independence and institutional reform complicates efforts to create a transparent, predictable business environment.

Declining Population, Rising Workforce

The Western Balkans are experiencing a demographic shift with a declining overall population but an increasing proportion of working-age individuals. This trend presents both challenges, such as a shrinking domestic market, and opportunities for a more competitive labor market. Effective policies focusing on education, employment opportunities, and talent retention are crucial to leverage this demographic advantage.

Western Balkans as Nearshoring Destination

The Western Balkans are emerging as an attractive nearshoring destination for European companies, thanks to their proximity, competitive wage levels, and skilled labor force. As companies seek to reduce supply chain risks and maintain greater control over production, this trend is likely to boost employment, attract foreign investment, and stimulate economic growth, positioning the region as a critical hub for European manufacturing and services.

Western Balkans as Friendshoring Destination

The trend of 'friendshoring,' which involves relocating supply chains to politically and economically allied countries, could lead to increased EU investment in the Western Balkans, particularly in economies that align closely with EU values and policies. However, countries with closer ties to Russia or China may see a reduction in European investments as EU companies prioritize partnerships with more politically aligned and stable markets.

Increasing Intra-Regional Trade in Services

Intra-regional trade in services within the Western Balkans is increasing significantly, driven by initiatives like CEFTA and the Common Regional Market Action Plan, which have reduced trade barriers, harmonized regulations, and improved infrastructure. This trend is fostering greater economic integration, enhancing resource allocation efficiency, and creating new business opportunities.

Boost in Backward Spillovers

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the Western Balkans is increasingly focusing on higher value-added activities, such as technology and research-intensive industries. This shift enhances the potential for backward spillovers, where local firms benefit from knowledge and technology transfers from foreign investors, leading to improvements in productivity, innovation, and the development of more sophisticated industries.

Competing Incentive Structures

The Western Balkans have successfully attracted FDI through various incentive structures, such as tax breaks and special economic zones. However, competition among the region's economies to offer better incentives may lead to a fragmented investment environment. This 'race to the bottom' could reduce the region's overall attractiveness to foreign investors, limiting sustained FDI growth and undermining efforts to create a unified, competitive market.

FDI Shift from WB to Ukraine

The post-war reconstruction of Ukraine could divert Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) away from the Western Balkans, as investors seek opportunities in Ukraine's larger market and strategic position within European supply chains. This shift, driven by reconstruction funds and Ukraine's geopolitical significance, may challenge the Western Balkans in attracting and retaining investment, potentially weakening the region's economic prospects and competitive position.

Digital Transformation of the Labor Market

The digital transformation of the labor market in the Western Balkans is accelerating, with increased adoption of AI, machine learning, and online platforms. While this shift offers opportunities for growth, it also highlights a significant digital skills gap. To fully benefit, the region must invest in upskilling its workforce to meet the demands of a digital economy.

Growing Skills Gap

The Western Balkans face a growing skills gap, especially in digital and technical fields. This is driven by inadequate investment in education, outdated curricula, and the emigration of skilled workers. As the demand for new skills rises with the twin transition to a digital and green economy, the region risks falling behind if it cannot equip its workforce with the necessary competencies.

Skills Mismatch Between Labor Supply and Demand

The misalignment between education systems and labor market needs in the Western Balkans is contributing to a growing mismatch where many young people are overqualified for available jobs, while key industries face skilled labor shortages. This ongoing trend is limiting job opportunities, hindering economic growth, and exacerbating youth unemployment.

Labour Emigration

Labor emigration continues to deplete the Western Balkans of its skilled workforce, as workers seek better opportunities abroad due to low wages, limited job prospects, and high corruption levels at home. This trend exacerbates the skills gap and weakens the region's human capital, posing significant challenges to economic development and competitiveness.

Diaspora Potential

The Western Balkans have a large diaspora that represents a significant, yet underutilized, resource for regional development. While there are efforts to engage the diaspora in knowledge transfer, investment, and business partnerships, these are often hampered by weak institutions and a lack of trust. Effectively tapping into the diaspora's potential could greatly enhance the region's economic prospects.

Youth Unemployment

Youth unemployment remains a critical issue in the Western Balkans, with rates significantly higher than in the EU. The region's young population faces a mismatch between education and labor market needs, limited job opportunities, and insufficient support for entrepreneurship. High youth unemployment not only stifles economic growth but also risks social instability as young people become disillusioned with their prospects.

Twin Transition

The Western Balkans are undergoing a twin transition toward a greener and more digital economy, driven by global demand for sustainable solutions and the need to comply with EU standards.

Successfully navigating this transition can open new markets, particularly in agriculture, energy, and digital trade, while also improving alignment with broader European economic trends.

Demand for Private Investment

The Western Balkans urgently need more private investment to support innovation and economic growth. Public funding alone is insufficient, and the lack of venture capital and private equity is a significant barrier. Attracting more private investment is essential for fostering a dynamic and competitive business environment, particularly for SMEs looking to scale up and innovate.

R&D Systematically Underfunded

The persistent underfunding of research and development (R&D) in the Western Balkans compared to EU levels continues to limit the region's capacity for innovation. As public research institutions struggle with limited resources and insufficient funding, the region faces ongoing challenges in driving technological progress, developing new products and services, and strengthening its overall innovation ecosystem.

Scattered Collaborations Between Academia and Business

Collaboration between academia and industry in the Western Balkans remains fragmented and limited. Despite growing efforts to promote these partnerships, the lack of strategic coordination continues to hinder the region's potential for innovation and weakens its competitive edge.

Underused potential of Smart Specialization Strategies

Smart Specialization Strategies can significantly boost competitiveness in the Western Balkans by focusing on areas of regional strength and fostering innovation-driven growth. Several economies are developing the Strategies, identifying priority sectors such as sustainable agriculture, energy, and manufacturing. Effective implementation and financing of these strategies can promote innovation, enhance regional economic integration, and better align the region with EU innovation goals.

Insufficient Support for International SME Cooperation

The Western Balkans recognize the importance of internationalizing SMEs for economic growth and innovation. However, this recognition has not been fully translated into actionable support. To boost international cooperation, the region needs stronger policies, better institutional frameworks, and initiatives that remove barriers and enhance the business environment, enabling SMEs to benefit from global opportunities.

Fragmented Digitalisation

Digitalization is a key driver of change in the Western Balkans, but its benefits are unevenly distributed. Inadequate digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas, and a lack of digital skills contribute to fragmented digitalization across the region. Economic inequalities, underperforming higher education, and urbanization trends are likely to exacerbate this fragmentation, hindering comprehensive digital transformation.

Deepening Integration into Global Value Chains

Global Value Chains (GVCs) are increasingly integrating international production, trade, and investment. For the Western Balkans, this presents an opportunity to strengthen their global competitiveness. To position themselves effectively in GVCs, the region must identify competitive advantages, invest in emerging sectors, and develop innovative solutions that align with global market demands.

Declining Infrastructure

The infrastructure in the Western Balkans, both physical and digital, continues to face significant challenges. Ongoing low fiscal capacity, weak institutions, and poor regional coordination remain major obstacles to long-term investment. Political tensions further impede the development of the infrastructure necessary for a fully integrated regional economy.

Growth Disparities

Economic and infrastructure development in the Western Balkans is often concentrated in capital cities, leaving smaller towns and rural areas behind. This creates significant growth disparities within the region. As clusters of excellence and innovation develop, these disparities may widen, driving further urbanization and uneven regional development.

Slow Reforms on Energy Transition

Among others, the European Commission's "European Green Deal" will introduce reforms that seek to accelerate the clean energy transition. While the Western Balkans are bound by international commitments such as the Paris Agreement, to date, few far reaching policies have been implemented. Not investing in a transition towards greener energy options might have high economic costs until 2035 and beyond.

Shift Towards Green Economy

A Green Economy focuses on sustainable growth driven by investments that reduce carbon emissions, enhance energy efficiency, and conserve biodiversity. For the Western Balkans, key areas include sustainable waste management, green entrepreneurship, eco-friendly tourism, and conservation projects. These initiatives are already influencing the region's development and hold significant potential for future growth.

Rising Economic Damage from Climate Change

The economic impact of climate change is increasing across the Western Balkans, with billions of euros in damage already recorded in agriculture alone. As extreme weather events become more frequent, other key sectors like forestry, fisheries, and tourism are also facing growing threats, disproportionately affecting this climate-vulnerable region.

Strategic Importance of New Technologies

The adoption of digital tools, AI, and advanced manufacturing is becoming increasingly critical for the Western Balkans. Early adoption and customization of these technologies are driving innovation, boosting productivity, and opening new markets, particularly in agriculture, education, and energy. This trend is essential for enhancing regional competitiveness.

Slow RD&I Growth and Technology Diffusion

Research, Development, and Innovation (RD&I) in the Western Balkans is progressing slowly, which limits the region's ability to capitalize on new growth opportunities. The slow pace of technology diffusion hampers economic progress, but Smart Specialization Strategies offer potential pathways to address these challenges and accelerate innovation.

Changing Demographics

Population decline is accelerating in the Western Balkans, with significant reductions expected in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, and Serbia by 2050. This demographic shift poses serious challenges to pension systems, healthcare, and labor markets, making it increasingly difficult for companies to attract and retain talent.

Rising Youth Entrepreneurship Amid Limited Government Support

Youth entrepreneurship is on the rise in the Western Balkans, spurred by the transition of many SMEs from first to second-generation ownership. However, the region still lacks sufficient government-led programs to foster entrepreneurial spirit and support startups, potentially limiting the full realization of this trend.

Underperforming Educational & Vocational Sector

The educational and vocational sectors in the Western Balkans are underperforming, as highlighted by the OECD's PISA assessments.

The region's ability to build a well-performing, innovative economy is at risk if education and training systems do not improve to meet the demands of a modern workforce.

Limited Career Opportunities for Researchers

Career opportunities for researchers in the Western Balkans remain limited, with few high-level academic positions available and a generally low reputation of the academic sector. This trend is contributing to the region's struggle to retain talent in research, development, and innovation.

Demand for Open Government

There is a growing demand for more open and participatory government across the Western Balkans, despite high levels of corruption. While most economies in the region have joined the global Open Government Partnership, the effectiveness of these initiatives is still limited, and citizens are increasingly calling for greater transparency and inclusion in policymaking.

The Centrality of Geopolitics

The trend from global cooperation to increased competition and fragmentation continues, with new threats emerging in areas like hybrid warfare, disinformation, and cyberspace. In the Western Balkans, this could manifest as heightened political tensions, increased vulnerability to external influence on media and elections, and challenges in cybersecurity, e.g., complicating the region's EU integration and stability.

Economic Challenges

Geopolitical fragmentation and the transition to climate neutrality are creating new threats to global economic growth. The sustained rivalry between the US and China, along with emerging regional blocs, will likely reshape global trade relations. For the Western Balkans, these shifts may result in economic uncertainty, making it harder to attract investment and integrate into global supply chains, while also navigating the transition to net-zero industries.

Environmental & Climate Crises

Climate change is accelerating, accompanied by widespread environmental degradation. The world is likely to overshoot the Paris Agreement targets, increasing the risk of climate tipping points. The

Western Balkans, with its diverse ecosystems and reliance on agriculture, is particularly vulnerable to climate impacts, such as extreme weather events and biodiversity loss, which could exacerbate socio-economic challenges and migration pressures.

Rising Use of Fossil Fuel

Global energy consumption is rising, and so is the use of fossil fuel – despite the increasing share of energy generated by renewables and their falling costs. The pace of the green energy transition may be slowed by investments in fossil fuels, critical mineral shortages, and limited electric grid capacity. The energy transition is likely to benefit some more than others and could open up new arenas of geopolitical competition, and social tensions within countries.

The Quest for Equality

Inequalities are growing in importance and complexity. Beyond economic inequalities, access to education, technology, healthcare, infrastructure, climate justice or intergenerational fairness are becoming increasingly relevant. In the EU and Western Balkans, these inequalities could exacerbate societal tensions, fuel political polarization, and weaken democratic institutions.

Technological Acceleration

The pace of technological deployment is accelerating, with increasing convergence across sectors. This is happening alongside rising expectations for technology to drive the green transition, amidst geopolitical rivalries and regulatory challenges. In the Western Balkans, rapid technological change may widen the digital divide, pose regulatory challenges, and create both opportunities and risks for economic development and labor markets.

Managing Health

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the need for well-resourced health sectors and underscored global interconnectedness, while widening the gap between rich and poor. The health sector will continue to be a driver of scientific and technological innovation. New treatments and therapies could bring huge dividends, while challenges such as anti-microbial resistance require close attention.

Changing Living Conditions

People are increasingly living in cities and are more exposed to the negative impacts of climate change. Technologies are changing the way we work and learn, bringing both opportunities and risks. On the one hand, there are new ways of working and delivering services; on the other, there are job losses and a pressing need for new skills. Both climate change and the twin digital and green transition will have strong and diverse impacts across the EU and Western Balkans.

Threats to Democracy

The trend towards democratic backsliding continues. Democracies are facing sustained attacks on their freedoms, including efforts to undermine elections, media independence, and judicial integrity. In the Western Balkans, these threats could manifest through increased political polarization, external interference, and challenges to governance, potentially slowing down democratic reforms and EU integration efforts, while destabilizing the region's political landscape.